

Team Competencies in Multinational Collaboration

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Abstract

The current studies examined cultural differences in schemata associated with the competencies required for effective team functioning. Participants (n = 163) completed a web-based survey designed to elicit prescriptive values and descriptions of typical practice of team competencies, using both an abstract instrument and vignettes that provided situational context. Overall, the results indicated that notions of competent team behavior rooted in Western scholarship are valued across a diverse set of countries, with respect to the typical practice in those countries. However, the competencies tended to be valued more in the U.S. than in three non-Western countries, as compared with respective practices. Surprisingly, these differences held even for team-focused competencies that would appear to run counter to Western independence and individualism, such as putting team goals before personal goals. Practical and theoretical implications are discussed.

Team Competencies in Multinational Collaboration

Cultural differences in group decision making, and team functioning more generally, are increasingly recognized as essential areas of investigation (Earley & Gibson, 2002; Elron, 1997; Jackson, May, & Whitney, 1995; Peterson, Miranda, Smith, & Haskell, 2003). This research trend largely mirrors corporate and government trends toward increasing reliance on multinational and multicultural teams to handle all manner of tasks, such as a multinational marketing team responsible for developing products for multiple-country markets or a team of coalition planners developing options for coordinating humanitarian assistance in response to a natural disaster. Trends toward greater use of multinational teams also imply some degree of evolution in the ways that professionals from participating nations think about what it means to be an effective team. The purpose of the current paper is to understand cultural differences and cultural transformation in the context of effective teamwork.

Before addressing culture in decision-making teams, we first need to define “culture.” As expected in any highly interdisciplinary field, there exist a variety of conceptions of culture (Atran, Medin, & Ross, 2005). Our conception is distinctly cognitive in nature, following an epidemiological perspective (Sperber, 1985). As such, a fundamental assumption about culture is that members of geographically proximal groups share experiences growing up in similar, but not identical, ecological and social contexts. These shared developmental experiences lead to reliable distributions of individuals’ mental representations, such as concepts, values, and schemata (Sperber & Hirschfeld, 1999). Such representational distributions, in turn, ground the distribution of behavioral norms, expectations, interpretations, and affective reactions in a population. Two important properties of these mental representations are that they are domain-specific and dynamic. That is, social activities, such as “collaborative decision making” or “teamwork,” are supported by representations that are tailored to those specific activities and susceptible to change. The result of many individuals altering their representations that pertain to particular contexts is adjustment in the overall distribution of representations. This is how we conceive of cultural change in specific contexts. Maznevski and Peterson (1997) provide an excellent example that highlights the importance of dynamic and domain-specific representations at the individual level in the context of effective teamwork (pg. 64):

For example, a Scandinavian member of a multinational executive team may have had experiences at an earlier career stage in “self-managed teams” in which all members were of equal status and made decisions by consensus. If the group was effective, then the member is likely to have a schema relating to “effective work group” that includes elements of equal status and consensus decision making. Events that conform to or contradict this schema are likely to be noticed and interpreted as good in the former case and bad in the latter. One day, our hypothetical Scandinavian may notice the event of all group members sitting together at a table. This event might be initially identified as a “group meeting,” because it conforms with group meetings the individual has experienced in the past. Its interpretation may evoke a set of scripts, including a norm to promote equal time talking for each member, calling a vote to determine the level of consensus, or pointing out when one member seems to be assuming a higher status than others. One the other hand, if this same member notices two members of the work group

chatting in the corridor, the event is unlikely to be placed in the category of “group meeting” and the related scripts will not be elicited.

In a multinational team, members’ countries are associated with distinct distributions of representations that would be triggered in the group setting. How, then, do cultural differences in representations affect the performance of decision-making teams? In research on group decision making, heterogeneity has been associated with improved decision quality, due to mediating factors such as increases in the considerations brought to bear on the decision, and reductions in the antecedents of groupthink (Hoffman & Maier, 1961; Janis, 1972; Maznevski, 1994; Yates, 2003). By extension, such effects would presumably apply to culture-based heterogeneity, in addition to within-culture distinctiveness. That is, the multinational group brings together people that have different, relevant background knowledge, as well as different frames for interpreting shared information (Maznevski & Peterson, 1997).

In contrast to the group decision literature, research into “team mental models” or “shared schemata” has tended to find that greater commonalities in mental representations are associated with improved team performance (Klimoski & Mohammed, 1994; Mathieu, Goodwin, Heffner, Salas, & Cannon-Bowers, 2000; Rentsch & Klimoski, 2001). Several hypotheses have emerged to reconcile these discrepant findings, including the nature of the task, the curvilinear relationships between the degree of heterogeneity and team effectiveness, and dimensions of heterogeneity (Earley & Mosakowski, 2000; Hambrick, Davison, Snell, & Snow, 1998). With respect to the “dimensions of heterogeneity” hypothesis, it seems likely that the domain of the schema or mental model is a likely determinant of heterogeneity effects on performance. For example, a team brought together with diverse knowledge about the task environment provides a net knowledge gain for the group. However, a team whose members possess discrepant schemata concerning the nature of teamwork, itself, is likely to suffer from process loss.

Differences in the schemata that define perceptions of effective teamwork should clearly be considered among the dimensions of representational heterogeneity that detract from group decision quality, and other aspects of team performance. However, depending on the resolution of the discrepancy and resulting success for that team, one or both members may leave with modified or broadened conceptions of effective team processes. For instance, a team including the Scandinavian, above, and an Indian member whose schemata include the unquestioning support of decisive leadership would clearly find themselves at odds over appropriate decision processes of the team. The resources relegated to detecting and resolving the discrepancies are likely to result in significant process losses. However, if the team is able to find its way toward successful reconciliation, then the members will leave with somewhat altered representations that expand the possibilities for conduct and interpretation of collaboration. Note that similar effects would be expected by cultural transmission via educational exchange.

The current article examines cultural differences and cultural change in representations associated with “team competencies” or “team performance functions” (Fleishman & Zaccaro, 1992). Team competencies refer to the requisite knowledge, skills, and attitudes of team members that enable effective performance of the team (Cannon-Bowers & Salas, 1997). Team competencies pertain to the team’s processes, whereas team performance refers to outcomes of the team’s work together, including goal accomplishment, satisfaction, and perceived efficacy.

Based on an extensive review of the literature on teamwork, Salas and colleagues have proposed that there are five core team competencies required for high performance (Salas, Guthrie, Wilson-Donnelly, Priest, & Burke, 2005; Salas, Sims, & Burke, 2005). These competencies include team leadership, mutual performance monitoring, backup behavior, adaptability, and team orientation. Taken together, Salas refers to these as the “Big Five” of teamwork. Beyond listing and describing these competencies, Salas, Sims, and Burke (2005) suggest universality in their applicability. For example, they propose that the focal competencies pertain regardless of the task the team is to perform. However, they do acknowledge that specific competencies may manifest differently depending on task demand. Furthermore, they do not restrict the Big Five’s domain to particular demographic or cultural groups, tacitly implying universality with respect to team composition, as well.

Nevertheless, recent research has questioned this assumption of universality, particularly with respect to the cultural composition of the team (Klein & McHugh, 2005). The core argument is that extant team competency taxonomies are based on research conducted in Western and Western European cultures. Because these taxonomies do not incorporate research from non-Western cultures, they may not generalize to cultures where members exhibit distinct behavioral, social, and cognitive patterns (Hofstede, 2001; Nisbett, 2003; Trompenaars & Hampden-Turner, 1998). Klein and McHugh (2005) conducted a qualitative study that has provided initial evidence that the Big Five competencies do conflict with the values associated with particular cultural backgrounds. For example, the Middle Easterners they interviewed reported that they do not regard back-up behavior by teammates as a positive behavior within a team, as it undermines the dignity and sense of self of the person being assisted. Furthermore, in cases where the overall competency category is accepted, the specific prescriptions can be quite different. For example, although “leadership” may be regarded as an important dimension of teamwork across many cultures, the appropriate roles and functions of the leader may be strikingly different. For instance, some Japanese interviewees reported that their leaders closely monitored their work, as well as quite personal activities, such as their finances. It is hard to imagine many Americans finding this to be acceptable leadership behavior.

It is important to clarify that Klein and McHugh’s findings have shown differences in typical practices and prescriptive value of the competencies, but they do not address the objective linkage between the proposed competencies and team performance. And doing so is not trivial. It is complicated at least in part by the dynamic nature of teams and cultures. There is a growing explicit recognition that team processes change over time, as individuals develop group-specific roles, routines, and expectations (Marks, Mathieu, & Zaccaro, 2000). Hence, universality in this case implies that teams that develop processes over time in accordance with the proposed competencies will achieve more effective performance than teams that do not, irrespective of the team composition or task environment. With respect to heterogeneous backgrounds, for example, it suggests that developing these competencies will improve team performance relative to current practice, even if the specific prescriptions diverge from the general distribution of schemata that constitute team members’ cultural backgrounds.

Nevertheless, even if the Big Five competencies have long-term value across cultures, understanding such potential incompatibilities is important, since they would slow or obstruct the acceptance and adoption of competent team behaviors. Furthermore, in multicultural teaming

arrangements with a short lead time for developing solutions (e.g., disaster response), the culturally distinct representations of the participants will have to be accounted for in defining how the team will work together effectively. In those situations, cultural differences in the representations associated with competent teamwork are sure to lead to process loss by contributing to violated expectancies and negative affective reactions. As noted above, the current research addresses cross-national differences in values for specific competencies in this spirit. It also seeks to address potential cultural change, as described next.

Much psychological research on cultural differences has emphasized differences in goals or values for certain behavioral tendencies (Grouzet et al., 2005; Hofstede, 2001; Schwartz, 1994), though it is also possible to examine perceived typicality of behaviors, of course. Furthermore, we propose that investigating the relationships between prescriptive values and typical practices can provide insight into potential changes in the distribution of representations in a culture. The idea stems from models of innovation adoption or social change (McGuire, 1989; Rogers, 1995). Such models attempt to describe the process by which individuals or organizations move from initial awareness of a new technology or idea, through evaluation, and ultimately to use or non-use of the innovation. For example, five stages comprise the innovation decision process proposed by Rogers (1995): Knowledge, Persuasion, Decision, Implementation, and Confirmation. In these models, changes in behavior (implementation) are generally preceded by the formation of favorable or unfavorable attitudes or values toward the innovation (persuasion), sometimes by considerable spans of time. Hence, the relationship between prescriptive values and descriptions of current typical practice provides an indication of the direction that cultural change is taking. For example, if the prescriptive value associated with a behavior tends to exceed current typical practice of that behavior, it provides an early indication that the behavior is gaining acceptance within the culture.

Indeed, such relationships between values and practices are likely to exist among managers on the contemporary global scene. In step with globalization and the continuing rise of multinational corporations, business education has contributed to the proliferation of Western conceptions of management and organizational behavior throughout the world. For example, 34% of the MBA students at the top five business schools are international students (*Global MBA*, n.d.). Also, management scholarship and education as practiced in non-Western countries is also strongly influenced by Western ideas. Furthermore, the diffusion of Western management scholarship very likely includes many of the ideas on what constitutes competent team practices as are captured in Salas, Sims et al.'s Big Five. If so, new knowledge on Western team competency ideals would not be expected to replace prior representations that underlie interpersonal and group behavior patterns. Instead, the discrepant ideas would all be stored in distinct representations. In particular, since education tends to affect declarative knowledge and attitudes more than behavioral routines, we propose that Western management scholarship influences beliefs about what constitutes good teamwork more strongly than it influences actual behavior. Indeed, some gap between prescribed values and descriptions of practice is expected in Western countries, as well, since they have not fully realized ideals from management scholarship. Hence, we hypothesize that judgments of the prescriptive value of Western team competencies will tend to outstrip judgments that describe actual practice, and that this effect will hold across countries. However, in line with Klein and McHugh's qualitative results, we also expect Western notions of teamwork to be valued and practiced more in Western than in

non-Western countries, since Western conceptions of teamwork are an outgrowth of Western culture. To summarize, we propose the following hypotheses:

Hypothesis 1: For Western and non-Western countries, judgments of the prescriptive value of core team competencies derived from Western research will exceed descriptive judgments of actual practice of those competencies.

Hypothesis 2: Prescriptive and descriptive judgments of the core team competencies will be larger for Western than non-Western countries.

Study 1: Survey

In Study 1, Hypotheses 1 and 2 were tested via a questionnaire survey approach. First, scale items were developed around each of five team competency dimensions, based on Salas, Sims et al. (2005) and related research. Probe questions were also created to elicit prescriptive and descriptive judgments for each item. The resulting questionnaire was then administered to business professionals in four countries, and the dimensionality reassessed by factor analysis. Scores on the final set of dimensions were then compared across the four countries in order to test the hypotheses.

In order to select team competency dimensions, we began by reviewing the Big Five dimensions recently proposed by Salas, Sims et al. (2005), along with the taxonomy previously developed by Fleishman and Zaccaro (1992). The Big Five framework was selected because of its purported comprehensiveness, and basis in an extensive review of the teamwork literature. Fleishman and Zaccaro also attempted a comprehensive taxonomy, and their highly detailed framework served as a check for completeness of the Big Five. The resulting set of teamwork dimensions were then reviewed in light of the results of a previous qualitative study of cross-cultural teamwork (McHugh, Smith, & Klinger, 2005). The study identified several Western team processes that occurred differently or did not occur at all in non-Western cultures. Table 1 describes the correspondences between these frameworks, and the resulting dimensions. As shown in Table 1, the following five categories emerged from an analysis of these three sources: decision processes and situation assessment, adaptability, performance monitoring, back-up behaviors, and motivation. A brief description of the sources and the resulting five teamwork dimensions follows.

Salas, Sims et al. (2005) proposed five core competencies that drive team performance: Mutual Performance Monitoring, Back-Up Behavior, Adaptability/Flexibility, Team Leadership, and Team Orientation. These five dimensions are described further in Table 1. In addition, Fleishman and Zaccaro (1992) proposed a taxonomy that focuses on functions that facilitate coordination between team members and tasks. These functions occur throughout all phases of team performance, including planning and execution. Their taxonomy, also shown in Table 1, consists of seven team performance functions with associated activity dimensions: Orientation Functions, Resource Distribution Functions, Timing Functions, Response Coordination Functions, Motivational Functions, Systems Monitoring Functions, and Procedure Maintenance Functions. Finally, McHugh et al. (2005) conducted a qualitative study using semi-structured and scenario-based interviews to identify how members of a variety of national cultures

collaborate, including how team members work together to make decisions, solve problems, and accomplish complex tasks. McHugh et al. (2005) identified cultural variations in teamwork processes corresponding to each of the Big Five dimensions, as well as some dimensions not covered by the Big Five, such as conflict management (also see Tinsley & Brett, 2001)

The dimensions that resulted from comparing these frameworks are displayed in Table 1, and described as follows. The Decision Processes and Situation Assessment category focuses on the roles of the leader and team member in the decision-making process and the path of information exchange within a team. The Adaptability dimension centers on the team's comfort with making changes to an existing plan. The Performance Monitoring category focuses on whether monitoring is done by all team members or only the leader. The Back-Up Behavior category investigates whether it is appropriate for team members to assist another team member who is having trouble completing a task. Finally, the Motivation category centers on the importance of individual recognition and success in relationship to team recognition and success.

As can be seen, these dimensions correspond closely with the Big Five. Two exceptions are the addition of the dimension corresponding to the team's assessment and decision process, and the removal of the leadership dimension. In reviewing the various categories, leadership functions seemed to be spread throughout the dimensions, rather than constituting a category that stands on its own. As will be seen from the factor analysis, however, leadership did in fact emerge as a distinct factor.

Method

Participants

A total of 163 business professionals (89 males and 74 females) participated in this study. Participants were recruited from the following nations: India ($N = 41$), South Korea ($N = 40$), Turkey ($N = 42$), and the U.S. ($N = 40$). We recruited individuals from India, S. Korea, and Turkey to ensure that we sampled a wide span of global cultural groups. These countries were selected because they provide a spread of rankings on Hofstede's (2001) dimensions of Power Distance, Uncertainty Avoidance, and Individualism/Collectivism (see Table 2). According to the country index scores for Power Distance, India ranked high in levels of Power Distance, while the U.S. ranked relatively low. In comparison, Turkey and S. Korea also had moderately high Power Distance scores. For Uncertainty Avoidance, Turkey and S. Korea had moderately high country index scores, and the U.S. and India had comparatively low scores. In addition, the U.S. had the highest-ranking score on the Individualism/Collectivism dimension, while the scores for India, Turkey, and S. Korea were lower.

Table 1

Team Competency Dimensions

Selected Dimensions	Salas, Sims et al.'s (2005) Big Five	Fleishman and Zaccaro's (1992) Team Performance Functions	Qualitative cross-cultural study (McHugh et al., 2005)
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Decision Processes and Situation Awareness 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> <i>Team Leadership:</i> Leaders create, foster, and maintain shared knowledge to enable effective teamwork 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> <i>Orientation Functions:</i> Information-gathering and information-sharing processes essential for mission completion <i>Timing Functions:</i> Tracking and regulating the time until task accomplishment <i>Response Coordination Functions:</i> Establishing coordination between member activities 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Leadership roles and decision-making processes may vary across nations (e.g., decisions made solely by the leader vs. decisions made through team consensus or voting)
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Adaptability 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> <i>Adaptability/Flexibility:</i> The ability to readjust actions or strategies to meet task requirements 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Most team performance functions take on an “adaptive” role during the execution phase 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Comfort with adaptation varies across cultures (e.g., replanning during a short timeframe or only when there is plenty of time)
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Performance Monitoring 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> <i>Mutual Performance Monitoring:</i> Members monitor each other's work and progress toward a goal 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> <i>Systems Monitoring Functions:</i> Processes for identifying and reporting performance errors <i>Procedure Maintenance Functions:</i> Processes ensure that the team is producing work that is up to performance standards 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Performance monitoring occurs differently in other cultures (e.g., who is responsible for monitoring—the leader or all team members?)
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Back-Up Behavior 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> <i>Back-Up Behavior:</i> The team members decision whether to “step in” for a fellow team member or shift work responsibilities to others who contain the appropriate knowledge, skills, and abilities 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> <i>Resource Distribution Functions:</i> Processes for assigning tasks to appropriate team members and balancing task load across members 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Back-up behavior may not occur in all cultures (e.g., these behaviors may conflict with the notions of honor and saving face)
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Motivation 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> <i>Team Orientation:</i> The tendency for team members to work in an interdependent manner in performing a group task, and the extent to which team members identify with the accomplishments of the team in relation to their own work performance 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> <i>Motivational Functions:</i> Processes for establishing performance norms, task commitment, and standards of success as well as processes to encourage team members to meet these standards 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Team orientation varies across nations (e.g., team orientation vs. explicit individualism vs. covert individualism)

Table 2

Country Index Scores and Rankings for Selected Dimensions (Hofstede, 2001, p. 500)

	India score (rank)	S. Korea score (rank)	Turkey score (rank)	U.S. score (rank)
Power Distance	77 (10-11)	60 (27-28)	66 (18-19)	40 (38)
Uncertainty Avoidance	40 (45)	85 (16-17)	85 (16-17)	46 (43)
Individualism/Collectivism	48 (21)	18 (43)	37 (28)	91 (1)

Individuals between the ages of 25 and 65 were recruited for this study. The average age of the participants who completed the study is 40.17 years ($SD = 9.87$). A one-way ANOVA revealed significant differences in age across countries, $F(3, 159) = 6.56, p < .001$. This difference was expected based on the participation requirements. Recruiting older participants (particularly older, female participants) in Korea for this study was challenging. They were less likely to work full-time in business settings and to be fluent in English; consequently, they were less likely to meet our participation requirements for inclusion in our sample. There were no other significant country differences for participant demographics. A summary of the demographic information is available in Table 3.

Table 3

Demographic Information by Country

	India	S. Korea	Turkey	U.S.	Total
Male (%)	54	50	60	55	55
Average Age (years)	39.6	35.2	41.5	44.3	40.2
Reading Comprehension (%)	87.8	90.0	80.9	90.0	87.1
College Graduate or higher (%)	100	100	95.2	70	91.4

All participants had at least some college education; 59.5% of the participants had college degrees and 31.9% had conducted post-graduate work. In addition, all participants were employed full-time in business settings, and they all had experience working in teams at their current place of employment.

All participants were fluent at reading and writing English. During the recruiting process, individuals from India, S. Korea and Turkey were asked to report their level of comfort with reading, writing, and conversing in English on a 5-point scale anchored at Strongly

Disagree (1) and Strongly Agree (5). To be eligible to participate, the individuals had to Strongly Agree (5) or Somewhat Agree (4) with the following statements: “I feel very comfortable reading books, magazines, and newspapers in English without any assistance,” and “I feel very comfortable writing in English without any assistance.” In addition, participants were given one scenario to review, and then they were asked to answer three comprehension questions about it. These questions provided an additional assessment of the participants’ English proficiency and of the participants’ engagement in the task. A final reading comprehension score was calculated based on whether the participant answered two or more questions correctly. A total of 87.12% of participants answered at least two reading comprehension questions correctly, and there were no significant differences by country, $F(3, 159) = 2.661, p = .572$.

Procedure

Participants were recruited by an international market research firm. Participants in India (Bangalore, Mumbai, Delhi, and Chennai) and the U.S. were recruited through an email containing a link to an online qualification screener. Participants in S. Korea (Seoul) and Turkey (Istanbul) were recruited by telephone solicitations. During the recruiting process, individuals answered several screening questions to determine their eligibility to participate. Participation was limited to individuals who met the following criteria: 1) between the ages of 25 and 65; 2) employed full-time as a business person or professional; 3) experience working in teams or work groups at current place of employment; 4) education level included at least some college; and 5) English fluency. Individuals who were qualified to participate were assigned an identification number and given the link to the web-based survey. The participants completed the online surveys in English from their home or their place of business. The surveys were conducted in English because that is commonly the language used on multinational teams, the domain of interest here (Earley & Mosakowski, 2000). The survey took approximately one hour to complete. Incentives were mailed to the participants upon completion of the survey. The amount of compensation for participation was comparable across all nations.

Materials: Scale Development

Initial development. Sixty-six items were developed to assess values and actual team functioning across cultures. The items were constructed according to the following five categories: decision processes and situation assessment, adaptability, performance monitoring, back-up behaviors, and motivation. Participants read statements about teamwork, such as “When a team member is having trouble completing a task, it is the other team members’ responsibility to help with the task,” and “To make a decision, the team discusses and debates different ideas and votes to make the final decision.” For each item, participants first considered whether, “*This is an example of good teamwork*” (prescription). Participants then rated their level of agreement with the item on a 7-point Likert-type scale anchored at Strongly Disagree (1) and Strongly Agree (7). After responses were made for all items, participants rated each item based on their agreement with the following statement in a different section: “*This is how teams actually work in my country*” (description). The items in each section were presented to participants in a randomized order.

Factor analysis. A principle components factor analysis with varimax rotation was conducted. The prescriptive and descriptive scores were collapsed across participants, so that each participant had two separate scores for each item. A four-factor solution resulted on the basis of the following criteria: 1) the Eigenvalue of all four factors was greater than one, and 2) the items in the first four factors were descriptive of a single construct.

The four factors that met the selection criteria explained 35.5% of the variance. The six items with the highest loadings for each factor were preserved, and the rest were discarded from the scale. The remaining items in each factor were assessed to determine whether they were cohesive in their representation of a single construct. As a result of this review, four additional items were eliminated, because they had a tenuous relationship with the other items. The four factors were then named to identify the construct they represented, and these constructs are described below (see Table 4).

Open Decision Process. The five items in Factor 1 reflect a decision-making process that involves participation of all team members, such as through discussion, debate, and/or voting. The highest loading item for this factor is: “The team makes decisions based on consensus of all members.” Cronbach’s alpha is .84.

Team Orientation. The four items in Factor 2 reflect a consideration for the team’s goals, in contrast to the goals of individual team members. The items for this factor were reverse scored. The highest loading item for this factor is: “When working on a team, team members look after their own best interest” (R). Cronbach’s alpha is .72.

Leadership. The three items in Factor 3 reflect the leader’s role in directing and coordinating the activities of other members. The highest loading item for this factor is: “When a team member is having trouble completing a task, it is the leader’s responsibility to redistribute task assignments.” Cronbach’s alpha is .48.

Team Support. The six items in Factor 4 reflect the ability of team members to shift workload and otherwise adjust to the situational demands of the team. The highest loading item for this factor is: “When a team member is having trouble completing a task, it is the other team members’ responsibility to help with the task.” Cronbach’s alpha is .71.

Table 5 contains the correlations between each subscale. All correlations were statistically significant, except for the correlation between Team Orientation and Leadership subscales. Interestingly, the strongest correlation was between Team Support and Open Decision Process. Importantly, Team Support-Team Orientation, and Open Decision Process-Leadership were not very highly correlated.

Table 4

Items and Factor Loadings for the Four Factors

<i>Items</i>	<i>M</i>	<i>SD</i>	<i>Loadings</i>
Factor 1: Open Decision Process	4.97	1.30	
The team makes decisions based on consensus of all members.	4.99	1.61	0.756
To make a decision, the team discusses and debates different ideas and votes to make the final decision.	4.97	1.63	0.747
To make a decision, the team debates the various ideas, weighs the pros and cons of each, and ultimately votes to make a final decision about which strategy to adopt.	5.16	1.62	0.673
Ideas are discussed and debated openly in team meetings.	5.30	1.64	0.643
All members of the team must agree with a decision before they can act upon it.	4.42	1.85	0.633
Factor 2: Team Orientation	4.64	1.36	
(R) When working on a team, team members look after their own best interest.	4.73	1.81	0.649
(R) Team members feel that their own individual recognition and praise is more important than the recognition of the team as a whole.	4.64	1.84	0.603
(R) Team members never help another team member finish a task.	4.68	1.96	0.592
(R) Team members do not want to help each other, because they do not want to make other teammates embarrassed or hurt their sense of dignity and self-worth.	4.53	1.79	0.588
Factor 3: Leadership	5.21	1.01	
When a team member is having trouble completing a task, it is the leader's responsibility to redistribute task assignments.	5.01	1.53	0.523
It is the team leader's responsibility to check in on members and monitor the progress toward their goals.	5.50	1.37	0.484
The team leader should make sure that the team is making progress toward its goals, not the members.	5.14	1.42	0.469
Factor 4: Team Support	4.62	1.05	
When a team member is having trouble completing a task, it is the other team members' responsibility to help with the task.	4.36	1.74	0.510
The team is comfortable with making changes to the plan even when the deadline is close.	4.12	1.70	0.454
Team members feel that the recognition and praise of the team as a whole is more important than individual recognition.	4.90	1.69	0.354
Team members watch each other's work in order to help when needed.	4.69	1.64	0.336
It is the team member's responsibility to step in and offer assistance when teammates are struggling due to higher workloads or responsibilities.	4.99	1.52	0.320
It is the team member's responsibility to step in and offer assistance when they do not have the appropriate skills to complete the task.	4.69	1.60	0.260

Note. $N = 326$.

Table 5

Correlations between Factors

	Team Support	Leadership	Team Orientation	Open Decision Process
Open Decision Process	.593*	.242*	.272*	1
Team Orientation	.282*	.077	1	
Leadership	.315*	1		
Team Support	1			

Note. * indicates significance at the .01 level.

Results

Once the four factors were identified and finalized, analyses were conducted to determine country differences. Except where noted, the results presented are based on a two-factor ANOVA with one between-subjects factor (country), and one within-subjects factor (probe question).

Open Decision Process

Prescriptive and descriptive scores for Open Decision Process are shown in Figure 1. There was a significant country effect on Open Decision Process subscale scores, $F(3, 162) = 4.556, p = .004$, and a significant difference between prescriptive and descriptive scores, $F(1, 162) = 52.596, p < .001$. The prescriptive scores were significantly greater than the descriptive scores on the Open Decision Process subscale. Additionally, the size of the difference between prescriptive and descriptive scores was dependent upon nationality, $F(3, 162) = 3.988, p = .009$. Fischer LSD post hoc multiple comparisons were calculated to determine the country effects on prescriptive and descriptive score differences. For the Open Decision Process subscale, Indians reported significantly smaller differences between prescriptive and descriptive scores than all other countries.

One-way ANOVAs with Fischer LSD post hoc multiple comparisons tests were calculated to further explore the country effect on prescriptive and descriptive Open Decision Process subscale scores. Prescriptive scores did not differ significantly by country, $F(3, 162) = .396, p = .756$; however, significant country differences were reported for the descriptive items, $F(3, 162) = 6.877, p < .001$. On the descriptive items, Indian participants reported scores that were significantly higher than participants in the other three nations. In addition, Korean participants reported significantly lower scores than U.S. respondents.

Team Orientation

Prescriptive and descriptive scores for Team Orientation are shown in Figure 2. There was a significant country effect on Team Orientation subscale scores, $F(3, 162) = 6.541, p < .001$, and a significant difference between prescriptive and descriptive scores, $F(1, 162) =$

66.664, $p < .001$. The descriptive scores were significantly greater than the prescriptive scores on the Team Orientation subscale. As with the Open Decision Process subscale, the size of the difference between prescriptive and descriptive scores was dependent upon nationality, $F(3, 162) = 9.615, p < .001$. Fischer LSD post hoc multiple comparisons were calculated to determine the country effects on prescriptive-descriptive score differences. For the Team Orientation subscale, participants from the U.S. had significantly larger differences between prescriptive and descriptive scores than all other countries, and Turkish participants had significantly larger differences than Indians and Koreans.

One-way ANOVAs with Fischer LSD post hoc multiple comparisons were calculated to determine country differences on prescriptive and descriptive subscale scores. Descriptive scores did not differ significantly by country, $F(3, 162) = 1.533, p = .208$. Significant differences were reported for the prescriptive items, $F(3, 162) = 13.499, p < .001$. For the prescriptive Team Orientation subscale, Indians reported significantly higher scores than participants in all other countries. In addition, U.S. participants reported significantly lower scores than participants in S. Korea and Turkey.

Leadership

Prescriptive and descriptive scores for Leadership are shown in Figure 3. There was a significant country effect on Leadership subscale scores, $F(3, 162) = 1.865, p = .138$, and a significant difference in prescriptive and descriptive scores, $F(1, 162) = 20.88, p < .001$. The prescriptive scores were significantly greater than the descriptive scores on the Leadership subscale. However, the difference between prescriptive and descriptive scores varied independently of nationality, $F(3, 162) = .444, p = .722$.

One-way ANOVAs with Fischer LSD post hoc multiple comparisons were calculated to identify country differences on prescriptive and descriptive Leadership subscale scores. There were no significant differences for either prescriptive or descriptive scales, $F(3, 162) = 2.434, p = .067$ and $F(3, 162) = 2.033, p = .111$, respectively.

Team Support

Prescriptive and descriptive scores for Team Support are shown in Figure 4. There was a significant country effect on Team Support subscale scores, $F(3, 162) = 13.189, p < .001$, and a significant difference in prescriptive and descriptive scores, $F(1, 162) = 50.788, p < .001$. The prescriptive scores were significantly greater than the descriptive scores on the Team Support subscale. Additionally, nationality significantly affected the difference between prescriptive and descriptive scores, $F(3, 162) = 5.956, p < .001$. Fischer LSD post hoc multiple comparisons were calculated to determine the country effects on prescriptive-descriptive score differences. For the Team Support subscale, Indians reported significantly smaller differences than Turkish and U.S. participants, and the U.S. participants reported significantly larger differences than Korean and Indian participants.

One-way ANOVAs with Fischer LSD post hoc multiple comparisons were calculated to determine country effects on prescriptive and descriptive subscale scores. Analyses revealed

significant nation differences for the prescriptive and descriptive Team Support subscale, $F(3, 162) = 11.508, p < .001$ and $F(3, 162) = 10.157, p < .001$, respectively. For the prescriptive items, participants in India and the U.S. reported significantly higher scores than Korean and Turkish participants. For responses to the descriptive items, Indian participants reported significantly higher scores than participants in the other three countries.

Summary

A factor analysis of 66 items about team performance and team processes was conducted. Four teamwork dimensions emerged from the data: Open Decision Process, Team Orientation, Leadership, and Team Support. These factors are largely consistent with Salas et al.'s (2005) Big Five dimensions. An important exception was that performance monitoring, backup behavior, and adaptability were all captured within a single factor that we labeled "Team Support." Also, the nature of the decision process was an additional factor not captured in Salas' framework. We briefly review the country comparison results by subscale, and then summarize the findings in terms of Hypotheses 1 and 2.

For the Open Decision Process subscale, individuals across cultures reported believing that more openness in decision processes are needed, relative to actual practice. The exception was India, in which value and behavior judgments were quite close. For Team Orientation, people across nations reported that team members should have more of a team orientation than they actually do. The differences between values and practice were far greater in the U.S. than in India, with S. Korea and Turkey falling in the middle. This effect was driven by rather striking differences in prescriptive judgments, with the U.S. placing the strongest value on Team Orientation. This result contrasts sharply with casual considerations of U.S. independence and individualism, and so is discussed further in the General Discussion. As for the Leadership subscale, participants reported valuing more direction and coordination from leaders than is currently exhibited in practice. This pattern was seen across cultures, and there were no major country effects. Finally, for Team Support, people across nations reported a greater value for more support behaviors, in relation to typical behavior. This effect is most apparent for the U.S. and least noticeable for India.

Across all countries and factors, teamwork values were more aligned with team competencies based on Western scholarship than were the actual behaviors. There were no effects in the opposite direction for any country. Hence, Hypothesis 1 was supported. With respect to Hypothesis 2, there was a trend of higher scores in the U.S., overall, though that result was driven more by differences in the prescriptive than in the descriptive judgments. In fact, there was no clear overall trend of country differences for the descriptive judgments.

Figure 1. Prescriptive and descriptive scores on the Open Decision Process subscale.

Figure 2. Prescriptive and descriptive scores on the Team Orientation subscale.

Figure 3. Prescriptive and descriptive scores on the Leadership subscale.

Figure 4. Prescriptive and descriptive scores on the Team Support subscale.

Study 2: Vignettes

In Study 1, we elicited judgments of prescriptive value and descriptions of typical behavior about team competencies which were stated as abstract principles in a questionnaire. In Study 2, which was conducted concurrently with Study 1, we elicited the same kinds of judgments but in response to vignettes in which various elements of teamwork were depicted.

The idea behind the use of vignettes was that people may agree on what is important when judging principles in the abstract, but then interpret displayed behaviors quite differently in context. This is because there are many elements that can be attended to in a context-rich situation, and that diversity allows for a greater range of differences in what representations are activated or in how the situation is “read.” Hence, more complex stimuli such as vignettes should be more sensitive to cultural differences than abstract questionnaire items. The questionnaire, on the other hand, provides greater clarity as to the precise nature of the dimensions on which the cultures differ.

We developed four vignettes for use in Study 2. Two of the vignettes displayed team behaviors that are generally consistent with Western scholarship on team competency, whereas the other two displayed team behaviors that would be inconsistent. Also, two of the vignettes were intended to focus on the leadership style and nature of the decision process, whereas the other two generally emphasized team orientation and team support. However, as discussed above, the vignettes do not line up precisely with specific factors. These two dimensions were counterbalanced in the vignette construction. In sum, four vignettes were used to determine whether Hypotheses 1 and 2 would hold with context-rich stimuli.

Method

Participants

The participants were the same as in Study 1.

Procedure

The procedures for recruiting participants and administering the survey were the same as in Study 1.

Materials

Participants read four vignettes, or scenarios, that described specific experiences of people working on a team in a business setting. The vignettes were developed based on incidents of teamwork collected during a previous qualitative study of multinational collaboration (McHugh et al., 2005). Each of the scenarios focused on different aspects of teamwork and team performance (see Table 6). Vignette 1 described a team making decisions based on open debate and discussion. In contrast, Vignette 2 focused on a team that had a hierarchical decision process with closed communications. Vignette 3 portrayed cooperative

Table 6

Teamwork Vignettes

Vignette 1: Marketing Strategy

Michael works in a software development company. He is leading a six-person marketing team. The marketing team has a new task to do. Recently, the company designed a new type of software that allows users to create musical scores. Michael's team has been tasked with selecting marketing strategies for this new software. The strategy will need to be presented to management in one week.

There are many ways to market the software. Michael asks each team member to develop ideas for a strategy. During a team meeting, each member shares his/her ideas about marketing strategies. The team members debate the ideas that are presented. The team members discuss the benefits and drawbacks of each idea. Several members express disagreement on the best strategy. After discussing the different viewpoints, the team members make a decision together about which strategy to adopt.

Vignette 2: Strategic Planning

Amal is the leader of his company's strategic planning team. The team is determining where the company wants to be in five years, and what its priorities are. The team makes decisions about how to distribute funds across the company over the next several years.

Currently, Amal's team is working on a plan for how to distribute funds across the different departments for the next year. Amal and his team have scheduled a meeting for next week to develop the plan to present to management.

Prior to the meeting, Amal speaks with each member of the team privately. He asks for their ideas about a plan for distributing funds. He does not share these ideas with other members because he doesn't want to embarrass anyone. Members may feel bad if their ideas have flaws. Amal uses the information gathered from these private discussions to make a final decision about the plan. In the meeting, he announces his decision. Though some of the team members privately disagree with the decision he makes, everyone expresses agreement with it out loud.

Vignette 3: Feasibility Testing

Daniel works for an electronics manufacturer. He is a member of a four-person team that is testing the feasibility of new cell phone features. The team is evaluating four features. Each team member is responsible for studying one feature. At the end of the study, the team will compile the results and present them to management.

While Daniel is talking with one of his teammates named Seth, he finds out that Seth is behind schedule on his task. The task is more challenging than the team had expected, and Seth might not have the skills necessary to complete it. Management expects a report on all four features, so it is important that the task be completed.

When Daniel realizes that Seth is behind schedule on his task, he decides to help. Daniel feels it is his responsibility to step in and offer help in cases where his teammates are struggling due to higher workloads or task difficulty. When Daniel offers his help, Seth accepts his offer. He is very appreciative of Daniel's help. Seth would do the same thing if Daniel had been struggling with his task.

Vignette 4: Copy Editing

Barak is an editor at a publishing company. He works on a team with four other editors. The team is managed by the chief editor. This week, the team has a total of ten book manuscripts to edit. Each member of the team is responsible for editing two or three of them. The chief editor asks the team to send him a progress report mid-week.

On Tuesday afternoon, Barak is having a conversation near the work area of one of his teammates. For a few moments, he glances down at one of the books his teammate is editing. He wants to see how much progress his teammate is making in comparison to himself. As he's looking, he notices some editorial mistakes in the manuscript.

When Barak notices the possible editorial mistakes in the manuscript, he decides not to look at the manuscript closer or to talk to his teammate about it. He believes it is the chief editor's responsibility, and not his, to monitor progress toward goals and the quality of the team members' work. In addition, he wants his boss to see that he's performing better than his teammate is.

teamwork and support behaviors. Vignette 4 depicted a team member acting in his own best interest in a collaborative setting.

After reading each scenario, the participants first rated whether the story was an example of good teamwork (prescriptive), and then they rated how well the story matched how teamwork actually occurs in their country (descriptive). Then, they moved to the next scenario.

Results

As in Experiment 1, the results presented are based on a two-factor ANOVA with one between-subjects factor (country) and one within-subjects factor (probe question), unless otherwise noted.

Vignette 1: Marketing Strategy

Prescriptive and descriptive scores for Vignette 1 are shown in Figure 5. As shown, there was a significant country effect, $F(3, 162) = 5.079, p = .002$, and significant differences between prescriptive and descriptive scores, $F(1, 162) = 89.564, p < .001$. For Vignette 1, the prescriptive scores were significantly greater than the descriptive scores. Furthermore, the size of the prescriptive-descriptive difference was dependent upon nationality, $F(3, 162) = 6.418, p < .001$. Fischer LSD post hoc multiple comparisons were calculated to determine the country effects on the differences between prescriptive and descriptive scores. For Vignette 1, the differences between prescriptive and descriptive scores were smaller for Indians than for all other nationalities.

One-way ANOVAs with Fischer LSD post hoc multiple comparisons were calculated to identify country differences on prescriptive and descriptive items. Significant country differences were identified for the prescriptive item, $F(3, 162) = 10.079, p < .001$. For the prescriptive item, Indians reported significantly lower scores than participants in all other countries. Descriptive scores did not differ significantly by country, $F(3, 162) = 1.561, p = .201$.

Vignette 2: Strategic Planning

Prescriptive and descriptive scores for Vignette 2 are shown in Figure 6. There was a marginally-significant country effect on Vignette 2 scores, $F(3, 162) = 2.501, p = .061$, as well as significant differences between prescriptive and descriptive scores, $F(1, 162) = 24.436, p < .001$. For Vignette 2, the descriptive scores were significantly greater than the prescriptive scores. However, the difference between prescriptive and descriptive scores did not depend on nationality, $F(3, 162) = 1.916, p = .129$.

One-way ANOVAs with Fischer LSD post hoc multiple comparisons were calculated to identify country differences on prescriptive and descriptive items. Significant country differences were identified for the prescriptive item, $F(3, 162) = 2.03, p = .042$. For the prescriptive item, Indians reported significantly higher scores than U.S. participants. Descriptive scores did not differ significantly by country, $F(3, 162) = 1.750, p = .159$.

Vignette 3: Feasibility Testing

Prescriptive and descriptive scores for Vignette 3 are shown in Figure 7. As can be seen, there was a significant country effect on Vignette 3 scores, $F(3, 162) = 3.363, p = .020$, and significant differences between prescriptive and descriptive scores, $F(1, 162) = 75.085, p < .001$. For Vignette 3, the prescriptive scores were significantly greater than the descriptive scores. Furthermore, the size of the prescriptive-descriptive difference was dependent upon nationality, $F(3, 162) = 5.246, p = .002$. Fischer LSD post hoc multiple comparisons were calculated to determine the country effects on the differences between prescriptive and descriptive scores. For Vignette 3, India reported smaller differences than S. Korea. India and Turkey both reported smaller differences than the U.S.

One-way ANOVAs with Fischer LSD post hoc multiple comparisons were calculated to identify country differences on prescriptive and descriptive items. Significant country differences were identified for the prescriptive item, $F(3, 162) = 7.911, p < .001$. For the prescriptive item, S. Korea and the U.S. reported significantly higher scores than participants in India. In addition, U.S. participants reported significantly higher scores than Turkish participants. Descriptive scores did not differ significantly by country, $F(3, 162) = 0.067, p = .977$.

Vignette 4: Copy Editing

Prescriptive and descriptive scores for Vignette 4 are shown in Figure 8. The country effect on Vignette 4 scores was not significant, $F(3, 162) = 1.286, p = .281$. As with the other vignettes, there were significant differences between prescriptive and descriptive scores, $F(1, 162) = 99.31, p < .001$. For Vignette 4, the descriptive scores were significantly greater than the prescriptive scores. The size of the prescriptive-descriptive difference was dependent upon nationality, $F(3, 162) = 3.966, p < .009$. Fischer LSD post hoc multiple comparisons were calculated to determine the country effects on the differences between prescriptive and descriptive scores. For Vignette 4, the differences between prescriptive and descriptive scores were smaller for India than for Korea and the U.S.

One-way ANOVAs with Fischer LSD post hoc multiple comparisons were calculated to identify country differences on prescriptive and descriptive items. Significant country differences were identified for the prescriptive item, $F(3, 162) = 3.181, p = .026$. For the prescriptive item, participants from India and Turkey reported significantly higher scores than participants in S. Korea and the U.S. Descriptive scores did not differ significantly by country, $F(3, 162) = 0.924, p = .431$.

Figure 5. Prescriptive and descriptive scores by country for Vignette 1, Marketing Strategy.

Figure 6. Prescriptive and descriptive scores by country for Vignette 2, Strategic Planning.

Figure 7. Prescriptive and descriptive scores by country for Vignette 3, Feasibility Testing.

Figure 8. Prescriptive and descriptive scores by country for Vignette 4, Copy Editing.

Summary

The country comparison results are summarized by vignette, and then discussed in relation to Hypotheses 1 and 2.

For Vignette 1, people across cultures reported valuing the open debate process more than it actually occurs in practice. This effect was smaller for India than other countries. For Vignette 2, individuals across nations reported that private meetings and sole leader decision making should be done less than it actually is. This effect did not depend on culture. For Vignette 3, people across countries reported that member-to-member support behaviors (without leader intervention) should occur more than it actually does. This effect was strongest for the U.S. and weakest for India, with S. Korea and Turkey in between. For Vignette 4, people across cultures reported that team members try to benefit by allowing other team members to fail, more often than it should occur. The effects were strongest in the U.S. and S. Korea, and the weakest effect was in India.

As in Study 1, Hypothesis 1 was supported. Teamwork values were more aligned with western team competencies than were actual behaviors, across all countries and vignettes. There were no effects in the opposite direction for any country. Again, consistent with Study 1, there was a trend of higher scores in the U.S., with the result being driven more by differences in the prescriptive rather than the descriptive judgments. Therefore, Hypothesis 2 was supported.

General Discussion

The studies reported in this article provide consistent evidence that Western prescriptions of competent teamwork are valued across a diverse set of countries, with respect to the current team practices in those countries. Overall, the gap between values and actual practice of team competencies tended to be the largest in the U.S. and the smallest in India. These differences seemed to be driven largely by U.S. respondents assigning higher values to the teamwork dimensions. When looking at prescriptive and descriptive judgments separately, there were no clear overall patterns of difference in the descriptive ratings across the countries. There was, however, an overall tendency for U.S. respondents to place more value on team orientation and team support than respondents from the three non-Western cultures. Also, when considering the vignettes (but not the scale items), Indian respondents appeared to endorse open decision processes less than the other three countries.

Theoretical Implications

There are several theoretical implications of the current studies. First, there are implications for taxonomies of team competencies. Salas, Sims et al. (2005) conducted an extensive review of the teamwork literature, and proposed five core competencies that lead to effective team performance. In Study 1, we found four factors that were reasonably consistent with the Big Five, though two exceptions were noteworthy. First, three of the Big Five, Performance Monitoring, Back-Up Behavior, and Adaptability, were captured within a single

factor, "Team Support," in Study 1. Second, "Open Decision Process," was suggested as an additional factor of interest.

A second theoretical implication has to do with the relation between domain-general values for social-interaction patterns (e.g., independence/interdependence), and values that apply to the specific domain of team interactions. One possibility is that a direct mapping exists from the general to the specific, so that anticipation of cultural differences in specific situational contexts can be reasonably performed using the domain-general values. The current results for team orientation and team support provide striking evidence against the validity of the direct mapping approach. Specifically, one might suspect that individuals from interdependent cultures would be more inclined to value and exhibit a team orientation than those from independent cultures (Markus & Kitayama, 1991; Trompenaars & Hampden-Turner, 1998). Indeed, interdependent cultures tend to encourage the subordination of personal interests to the goals of the larger work group, in addition to encouraging cooperation, group harmony, a concern with group welfare, and an equal distribution of rewards. Independent cultures, on the other hand, place more emphasis on self-orientation, self-sufficiency, individual autonomy, the pursuit of personal goals that may or may not be consistent with the group's goals, competition, and individual-based rewards (e.g., Trompenaars & Hampden-Turner, 1998). Based on these characteristics, it would be logical to expect members of collectivistic cultures to value team orientation and team support behaviors more than members of individualistic cultures.

However, the data in the current study indicate the opposite. The most independent participants (those from the U.S.) value team orientation and team support behaviors more than the more interdependent members of non-Western countries. Though puzzling, this finding is consistent with recent work investigating differences in team-related behaviors across cultures (McHugh et al., 2005). Interviews with participants from India and China revealed an interesting tension between team orientation and a sense of individual rivalry. Every participant interviewed from India, and many of the participants from China, discussed the presence of intense competitiveness and rivalry in their work teams. The majority of participants acknowledged the merits of working together and putting the goals of the group at the forefront. Yet, they also expressed the desire to outperform their teammates. It was particularly important to them that their team leader or manager was aware of how they distinguished themselves from their teammates. Though this competitiveness was described as having a strong presence in teamwork, both Indian and Chinese participants also acknowledged that it is relatively covert and seldom discussed openly.

In addition to team orientation, McHugh and Smith found evidence that team support behaviors may not be valued within collectivistic cultures to the extent that one might expect. Interviews with Middle Easterners, in particular, have indicated that support behaviors within a team might be an uncommon or an uncomfortable practice. One potential explanation for this seeming contradiction might be related to the notion of honor or "face" that is interwoven throughout collectivistic cultures (Feghali, 1997; Patai, 2002). Team members may refrain from exhibiting support behaviors such as performance monitoring or back-up behavior due to a concern that it could dishonor their colleague or cause him/her to lose face or dignity. This would be particularly likely in situations where a team member's aid might suggest that the individual being supported is somehow incapable of performing the task without assistance.

Much fruitful psychological research has been conducted with the intent to characterize cultural differences in terms of a small number of dimensions. This approach has obvious appeal, since it promises that a little information can yield a wide range of inferences about the behavior of people from other cultures. Reducing the complexity of cultural knowledge in this way is attractive, but the general predictive value is not apparent and may be quite limited. The current findings suggest that aspects of mental representations pertaining to the specific application domain of interest should be assessed instead.

Practical Implications

The current studies have revealed that a degree of cross-cultural consensus appears to be forming regarding what counts as good teamwork. With respect to current practices, respondents in four diverse countries expressed team values in a direction that is consistent with Western management scholarship on team functioning. Nevertheless, national differences in team competency values do exist, and such discrepancies can result in practical consequences for team performance, especially if they are not recognized. How, then, can such differences be ameliorated?

One potential approach is to develop cultural sensitivity in managers to such differences through training and education. For instance, managers could receive instruction on national profiles concerning team competency values, along with potential recommendations for dealing with these value differences. There are, however, several problems with this approach. One problem is that the promotion of such national values can lead to stereotyping, as well as a static conception of culture. Since, for example, cultural values are not uniformly shared among a society's members (Rohner, 1987), and the spread can be quite large, predictions about a team member's values based on their nationality are most likely to be incorrect. The problem is compounded by the fact that cultures change over time. Another problem is that the emphasis and manifestation of team competencies is expected to be task specific, even if universality of the overall dimensions is granted (Salas, Sims et al., 2005). Hence, there is a need to ground the details of competent team interactions in the specific situation that the team is facing, something that generic training on national differences in competency values does not permit.

An alternative approach is to develop interventions that aid in the creation of "hybrid" or "third" cultures (Casmir, 1992; Earley & Mosakowski, 2000). A hybrid culture refers to the culture that develops after the team has formed, based on mutual interactions. The team's initial interactions lead to the emergence of simplified sets of shared mental representations, including rules and expectations for interactions and task accomplishment, and perceptions of the members and team itself. Schemata and values would both be included among the emergent shared mental representations. Note that the idea of a hybrid culture possesses a domain-specific connotation; it addresses the question of how will a particular multinational team, embedded in a specific situation, interact, make decisions, and get work done. The general idea, then, is to influence the initial interactions of such teams in a way that promotes the emergence of effective hybrid cultures. In a qualitative study, Earley and Mosakowski (2000) found that high-functioning multinational teams were more likely to decide on ground rules or procedural matters up front in the first meeting, whereas lower performing teams never developed clear, consistent rules for

engagement. From the standpoint of the current research, in addition to devoting initial meeting time to matters of procedure, a fair portion of that time ought to be spent discussing team competencies, or addressing the question of “What does a high-performing team look like in this situation?” There is also a value in unpacking that question in terms of the dimensions explored here, since team members would be less likely to assume there would be no disagreement with something as fundamental as team support, for example. Furthermore, since members from some cultures might well be uncomfortable airing divergent views (and no “hybrid” procedure has as yet been developed by the team), one possibility is to have them fill out a questionnaire or survey such as in Study 1 prior to the meeting. The leader could then decide on how best to handle the divergence (e.g., open in a full meeting, or with individuals prior to a full meeting).

A description of a calibration tool based on the survey and dimensions from Study 1 is presented next. Although similar cultural calibration tools may exist, what makes the current tool unique is that it focuses precisely on the dimensions most relevant to developing high-performing teams.

Calibration of Collaborative Styles

As we envision it, the calibration tool provides a snapshot of team members’ cultural collaboration profiles. The profile is constructed based on individual responses to the teamwork values assessment instrument. The profile contains scores on each of the four critical teamwork dimensions that were identified during this study: Open Decision Process, Team Orientation, Leadership, and Team Support. Once the team members complete the assessment instrument, the cultural calibration profiles are calculated, and a chart depicting the results is made available to the leader.

This chart enables the leader to identify cultural differences in team members’ beliefs about what counts as good teamwork, which may hinder team functioning. Behavioral implications of these differences are also provided. Based on this information, the leader can identify specific points of friction among the members about team functioning. The tool may also recommend interventions that the leader can implement to overcome existing cultural barriers and improve team performance.

The calibration tool is flexible and can be used in variety of ways depending on the needs of a particular team. For example, the leader can review the chart and develop interventions without sharing the results with the entire team. This method may be best for ad hoc teams working under a tight deadline, because there would not necessarily be time to work through the issues as a group. An alternative application of this tool is to share the results with the entire team and hold a group discussion about the cultural differences. The leader could facilitate the meeting as team members share their expectations about team functioning. This technique has the added benefit of promoting the construction of a hybrid culture across the team. As team members work through their differences, they tend to develop new beliefs and practices that all team members can use in the specific confines of the current team. This tool should be especially useful for teams where member rotations are commonplace, since leaders tend to have less time to understand their assigned team members in those settings. Finally, this tool may also be used before the team forms as a guide for staffing and team assignment.

Value Scores on Teamwork Dimensions		
	Low (1) ← (4) → High (7)	
Open Decision Process	A	Behavioral Implication & Intervention:
	B	
	C	
	D	
Team Orientation	A	Open Decision Process
	B	Team Orientation
	C	Leadership
	D	Team Support
Leadership	A	Member Key:
	B	
	C	
	D	
Team Support	A	A – Amal
	B	B – Kim
	C	C – Eser
	D	D – Jeffrey

Figure 9. Sample screenshot from the calibration tool.

Limitations and Future Directions

The current study has shed light on cultural differences in mental representations of team competencies, ways in which they differ from general cultural values, and how they might be detected and supplanted with hybrid team cultures. However, there are some limitations of the current study that need to be discussed. One problem is that this and similar past studies have started with Western conceptions of team competency taxonomies and addressed the question of whether the listed competencies apply across cultures. Although that tact has yielded fruitful results, it leaves a potential gap in the full range of competencies that might be considered. In particular, team member interactions that would be considered highly competent in non-Western cultures, may not be well represented. One widely-recognized concept that would surely be included among the competencies of team members in most non-Western teams, for example, is the concept of face (Tjosvold, Hui, & Sun, 2004). Such omissions may well reconcile apparent anomalies in the current findings. For example, it may be taken for granted that non-Westerners often do not voice disagreement, or have a difficult time doing so. However, it is quite possible that the issues of open conflict are more subtle, and that non-Westerners favor open discussion and debate, consistent with the current findings. Instead of being “anti-debate,” it might be better to think of non-Westerners as balancing debate with another critical factor, that of maintaining “face” of themselves and their teammates. Other competencies that are valued by non-Westerners, but that get less attention in Western management scholarship, may be missed as well. Such additional factors should be addressed in future research in order to develop a more complete assessment instrument and calibration tool. Furthermore, the dimensions of

decision process and conflict management were compressed in the current study, and should be expanded to include more detail in a subsequent iteration. A final potential issue has to do with the current emphasis on mental representations, values and schemata in particular. Both are clearly important for facilitating multicultural collaborations. However, a broader framework would also include demeanour and language as important attributes that are culturally determined (Hambrick et al., 1998). For example, eye contact and interruption patterns may well lead to frustration or mistrust, and also remain at a tacit level. Furthermore, overall facility with the team's language, or even slight differences in the meanings attached to terms can cause considerable disruption that detracts from the team's performance. Nevertheless, although teamwork values and schemata do not represent multinational collaboration issues at all levels of analysis, they do provide an excellent starting point for developing a hybrid culture. With the development of higher-level shared mental representations, a broad framework is established for the detection, negotiation, and reconciliation of differences that arise at the lower levels.

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